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CATALOGUE OF INDUSTRIAL STAKEHOLDERS

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List of acronyms

AMR	Antimicrobial Resistance
CEA	Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et aux Énergies Alternatives
CBE JU	Circular Bio-based Europe Joint Undertaking
DMP	Data Management Plan
EEN	Enterprise Europe Network
ERC	European Research Council
EU	European Union
HEU	Horizon Europe
IME	Fraunhofer Institute for Molecular Biology and Applied Ecology
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions
R&I	Research and Innovation
R&D	Research and Development
RTO	Research and Technology Organization
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The objective of the deliverable “**Catalogue of Industrial Stakeholders**”, prepared under Work Package (WP) 2 of *InnovAntiBiofilm* is to identify, map, and characterise relevant companies and organisations with potential interest in the development, validation, and uptake of sustainable antibiofilm solutions.

This catalogue provides an overview of industrial actors, sectoral associations, research and technology organisations (RTO), and other relevant entities operating across key areas of relevance to the project, including bioprocess and metabolic engineering, plant-derived antimicrobial production, pharmaceutical development and formulation, and regulatory consultancy and market access for antimicrobial products.

The methodology combined targeted desk research, expert consultation among consortium partners, and structured data collection. A survey template (Annex 1) was developed to ensure consistent profiling of stakeholders. The resulting list (Annex 2) includes detailed entries for each organisation, covering domains of activity, geographic scope, and potential engagement interests.

The engagement strategy set out in this document describes how stakeholders will be invited to participate in project activities, including newsletters, thematic workshops, training events, and consultations. Clear mechanisms are proposed to encourage two-way communication, gather feedback on project outputs, and lay the groundwork for long-term collaboration.

Insights emerging from this mapping highlight strong industrial interest in sustainable approaches to antimicrobial development, as well as challenges related to regulatory pathways and production scale-up. These findings will inform the design of forthcoming dissemination, exploitation, and sustainability actions in *InnovAntiBiofilm*.

This deliverable will serve as a living reference throughout the project, supporting ongoing stakeholder engagement and helping maximise the relevance, adoption, and impact of project results.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project Background

The *InnovAntiBiofilm* project addresses the urgent global challenge of biofilm-associated antimicrobial resistance (AMR), a growing threat to public health and industrial processes. Supported by the Horizon Europe framework, the project brings together leading researchers, industrial innovators, and stakeholders to develop groundbreaking solutions that target biofilm formation and persistence. Industrial stakeholders play a critical role in this mission, acting as key enablers for scaling and commercializing innovative technologies. This **Catalogue of Industrial Stakeholders** aims to be a vehicle to bridge the gap between scientific research and industrial application, fostering collaboration to maximise the project's impact across biotechnology, pharmaceuticals, and agriculture.

1.2. Purpose of the Catalogue

The purpose of this report is to identify, categorise, and profile industrial stakeholders relevant to *InnovAntiBiofilm*. By creating a comprehensive catalogue, the report aims to:

- Highlight the importance of industrial stakeholders in driving innovation and commercialisation.
- Facilitate collaboration between academia and industry to ensure the practical application of research findings.
- Provide a strategic tool for engaging stakeholders throughout the project lifecycle, ensuring alignment with project objectives and long-term sustainability.

This report serves as a resource for managing stakeholder relationships and as a foundation for future engagement activities, such as workshops, knowledge transfer sessions, and joint development projects.

1.3. Structure of the Report

This report is structured to provide a clear presentation of the industrial stakeholder landscape for *InnovAntiBiofilm*. The first section outlines the objectives and methodology used to identify and classify stakeholders, focusing on their relevance to the project's goals. This is followed by a detailed catalogue of industrial stakeholders, categorised by sector, geographic distribution, and areas of expertise.

The subsequent sections detail strategies for engaging stakeholders in project activities, with an emphasis on fostering collaboration and supporting commercialisation. The report concludes with a discussion on outcomes, insights, and plans for maintaining stakeholder engagement beyond the project's duration. Supplementary materials, including stakeholder profiles and tools for engagement, are included in the annexes to support effective implementation.

2. Objectives

Deliverable 2.1 plays a central role in achieving the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project's broader goals. This deliverable is directly aligned with the objectives of WP2, which aims to strengthen cooperation with industry, define clear exploitation pathways, and establish the foundations for long-term sustainability of project outcomes. Specifically, the primary objective of this deliverable is to facilitate meaningful collaboration between *InnovAntiBiofilm* and a broad spectrum of organisations, including industrial actors, companies, RTOs, sectoral associations, and other entities that can support the project, ensuring that the research outputs are translated into impactful and scalable solutions. Industrial stakeholders are instrumental in bridging the gap between scientific discovery and real-world application, and this report is designed to strategically identify and engage these stakeholders to maximise the project's success.

2.1. Strengthening Academia-Industry Collaboration

One of the key objectives of this deliverable is to establish a robust network of industrial stakeholders capable

of complementing and advancing the scientific efforts of *InnovAntiBiofilm*.

Effective collaboration between academia and industry is critical to *InnovAntiBiofilm*'s mission of addressing biofilm-associated antimicrobial resistance. This document supports this objective by identifying industrial stakeholders whose capabilities and expertise complement the project's academic research. Through the catalogue of industrial stakeholders, the report establishes a knowledge base that facilitates the alignment of research outcomes with industry needs.

By providing a detailed understanding of industrial actors and their specific roles, the report highlights potential pathways for collaboration. These collaborations can include co-development of innovative antibiofilm technologies, validation of research outputs in industrial settings, and scaling solutions to meet market demands. Strengthening these connections ensures that *InnovAntiBiofilm*'s scientific advancements are translated into practical, real-world applications, bridging the gap between discovery and deployment.

Ultimately, this deliverable emphasises the importance of integrating industrial stakeholders into the research ecosystem to foster knowledge exchange, resource sharing, and the co-creation of impactful solutions. The catalogue serves as a strategic tool to identify opportunities for collaboration, laying the groundwork for long-term partnerships that drive innovation and scalability.

2.2. Facilitating Knowledge Transfer and Commercialisation

Another significant aim of the stakeholder catalogue is to facilitate the transfer of knowledge and technologies developed during the project. Therefore, the report aims to identify industrial stakeholders who are well-positioned to adopt and scale the project's outcomes. By bridging research outputs with market needs, *InnovAntiBiofilm* can ensure that its findings are effectively translated into practical applications, such as new products, materials, or processes. This objective is critical to maximising the societal and economic impact of the project, particularly in combating biofilm-associated antimicrobial resistance.

2.3. Promoting Long-term Sustainability

Beyond the project's funding period, this deliverable also prioritises the long-term sustainability of *InnovAntiBiofilm*'s outcomes. Beyond the duration of the project, the stakeholder network established through this deliverable is envisioned to evolve into a lasting ecosystem. By fostering relationships that extend beyond the project timeline, *InnovAntiBiofilm* aims to secure ongoing support for research and development (R&D), including the pursuit of new funding opportunities and joint initiatives with industrial partners.

2.4. Addressing Industrial Needs

This catalogue aims to align *InnovAntiBiofilm*'s research with the specific needs and challenges faced by industrial stakeholders. By understanding their priorities and pain points, the project can tailor its research and development activities to provide targeted, impactful solutions. This approach ensures that the project remains relevant to industries such as biotechnology, pharmaceuticals and agriculture & food, while also addressing broader societal needs.

2.5. Supporting the European Research and Innovation Agenda

Finally, the deliverable aligns with the European research and innovation agenda, particularly the [European Partnership One Health Action Plan against Antimicrobial Resistance](#)¹ and the [Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe](#)². By integrating these strategic priorities, *InnovAntiBiofilm* contributes to addressing the urgent challenge of antimicrobial resistance and strengthens Europe's position as a leader in biofilm-related innovation.

Through these objectives, the stakeholder catalogue ensures that *InnovAntiBiofilm* is well-equipped to translate its scientific innovations into meaningful solutions that address global challenges, foster industrial collaboration, and drive sustainable impact.

¹ European Commission. EU Action on Antimicrobial Resistance. Available at: https://health.ec.europa.eu/antimicrobial-resistance/eu-action-antimicrobial-resistance_en

² European Commission (2020). Pharmaceutical Strategy for Europe. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0761>

3. Who are the *InnovAntiBiofilm* Industrial stakeholders

Industrial stakeholders are a cornerstone of the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project, serving as vital contributors to the development, validation, and commercialisation of antibiofilm solutions. These stakeholders represent organisations, enterprises, and entities operating within key industrial sectors that are directly impacted by or engaged in addressing biofilm-associated challenges. Their involvement is particularly critical in this field because biofilm formation presents unique and complex challenges that span across industries, including healthcare, agriculture, environment, food and feed production, and manufacturing.

Industrial stakeholders contribute to *InnovAntiBiofilm* in several ways:

- **Technical Expertise:** They bring specialised knowledge in areas such as metabolic engineering, bio-based technologies and antimicrobial development, which is essential for advancing antibiofilm innovations.
- **Resource Provision:** Industrial partners offer facilities, equipment, and financial support for testing, validating, and scaling up new solutions, accelerating the transition from laboratory research to real-world applications.
- **Market Insights:** With a deep understanding of market demands and industry trends, they help tailor the project's outputs to meet customer needs and ensure commercial viability.
- **Regulatory Guidance:** Their familiarity with industry regulations and standards assists in navigating the complex pathways required for product development and commercialisation.
- **Distribution Networks:** Established channels and networks facilitate the dissemination and adoption of new technologies, extending the project's reach and impact.

By engaging with these industrial stakeholders, *InnovAntiBiofilm* aims to bridge the gap between academic research and practical implementation, accelerating the development of effective antibiofilm strategies that can be readily integrated across various sectors.

3.1. Key Industrial Sectors

The industrial stakeholders involved in *InnovAntiBiofilm* come from several key sectors that both face significant biofilm-related challenges and possess the capabilities to contribute to their resolution. The primary sectors include:

Biotechnology Industry

The biotechnological industry plays a key role in advancing bio-based technologies to counteract biofilm-related issues. Professionals in this field contribute to the design and production of enzymes, peptides, or biomaterials that can prevent or degrade biofilms in medical, industrial, or environmental settings. Their ability to scale laboratory innovations into commercial products is crucial for ensuring the widespread adoption of these technologies across diverse applications. Their expertise enables the creation of innovative solutions that are biologically based, environmentally friendly, and effective across various applications.

Pharmaceutical Industry

In the pharmaceutical sector, biofilms significantly reduce the efficacy of traditional antimicrobials, making them a major barrier to treating persistent infections. Industry professionals, including drug developers and clinical researchers, contribute to *InnovAntiBiofilm* by discovering and developing new antimicrobial agents and treatments that specifically target biofilm-associated infections. Their involvement ensures that the project's outputs are aligned with clinical needs and can progress through the necessary stages of drug development, regulatory approval, and market introduction.

Agriculture & Food and Feed Industry

Biofilm formation presents significant challenges in the agriculture and food and feed industry, affecting food

and feed safety, shelf life, and processing efficiency. Stakeholders in this sector are focused on developing antimicrobial coatings, biofilm-resistant packaging materials, and sanitation strategies to mitigate bacterial contamination throughout the food and feed production and distribution chain.

Food and feed-processing facilities and agricultural operations are particularly vulnerable to biofilm-related contamination, which can lead to increased risks of foodborne illnesses and regulatory non-compliance. Therefore, collaboration with industry partners in this field is essential to developing eco-friendly antimicrobial agents, enzymatic treatments, and innovative surface modifications that prevent biofilm accumulation on processing equipment, packaging, and storage systems.

By integrating stakeholders from the food and feed and agriculture sectors, *InnovAntiBiofilm* aims to enhance food and feed safety standards, improve operational efficiencies, and reduce economic losses caused by biofilm-associated spoilage and contamination.

In addition to their technical capabilities, these stakeholders bring valuable knowledge of market dynamics and regulatory pathways, which are critical for navigating the complex landscape of antimicrobial resistance solutions. Their role in shaping and supporting the adoption of antibiofilm innovations underscores their importance as strategic partners in *InnovAntiBiofilm's* mission to combat AMR through cutting-edge, bio-based technologies.

3.2. Stakeholder Contributions

Industrial stakeholders are essential collaborators in *InnovAntiBiofilm*, bringing specialized expertise and practical resources that drive the project toward impactful outcomes. Their contributions span multiple dimensions, from research validation to commercialisation, ensuring that the project's antibiofilm solutions are robust, scalable, and aligned with industry needs. The primary areas of contribution by stakeholders include:

Research and Development Validation

Industrial stakeholders play a critical role in validating *InnovAntiBiofilm's* research outputs under real-world conditions. Companies in biotechnology, pharmaceuticals and food and feed and agriculture, provide the facilities, expertise, and systems required to test antibiofilm technologies in industrial settings. Their input helps refine and optimize solutions to meet performance expectations and compliance standards.

Co-Development of Solutions

Collaborating with academia, stakeholders co-develop solutions that integrate cutting-edge scientific innovations with practical industrial applications. For example, biotechnological firms contribute to the development of bioengineered enzymes, while pharmaceutical companies assist in tailoring therapies to target biofilm-associated infections. This co-creation process ensures that outputs are both scientifically advanced and market ready.

Market Insights and Alignment

With deep knowledge of market trends and customer needs, stakeholders provide valuable insights that guide *InnovAntiBiofilm's* research priorities. Their feedback helps align project outputs with industry demands, ensuring the solutions are relevant, competitive, and capable of addressing specific challenges faced by end-users.

Commercialisation and Scaling

Industrial partners are instrumental in scaling *InnovAntiBiofilm's* technologies from prototypes to market-ready products. Through their established production capabilities, distribution networks, and business acumen, stakeholders facilitate the widespread adoption of antibiofilm solutions across various industries, from healthcare to agriculture.

Regulatory and Standards Support

Navigating regulatory landscapes is a significant aspect of bringing innovative antibiofilm solutions to market. Stakeholders with expertise in regulatory compliance help ensure that project outputs meet legal, safety, and quality standards. This support is particularly vital in highly regulated industries such as pharmaceuticals, medical devices, and food and feed production.

Innovation Drivers

Stakeholders often drive innovation by identifying gaps in existing technologies and suggesting new areas of research. Their on-the-ground experience and industry-specific challenges provide a practical perspective that enriches the project's innovation process, leading to solutions that are not only effective but also tailored to real-world applications.

Outreach and Advocacy

Industrial stakeholders also play a role in advocating for *InnovAntiBiofilm's* solutions within their networks and industries. Their participation in workshops, conferences, and dissemination activities raises awareness about the project's outputs, encouraging broader adoption and creating opportunities for new collaborations.

4. Methodology

The methodology employed in the development of the **Catalogue of Industrial Stakeholders** is designed to ensure a comprehensive, inclusive, and systematic approach to identifying, categorising, and engaging stakeholders relevant to the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project. This section outlines the steps, criteria, and processes used to create a robust and actionable stakeholder catalogue.

4.1. Approach to identifying stakeholders

To develop a comprehensive and strategic **Catalogue of Industrial Stakeholders**, the *InnovAntiBiofilm* team employs a systematic, multi-step approach that ensures broad sectoral representation and relevance to the project's goals. The identification process follows these key steps:

a) Questionnaire for Consortium Partners

To ensure a comprehensive identification of industrial stakeholders, KPMG designed a structured questionnaire tailored to gather insights on relevant organisations from all consortium partners, leveraging their extensive professional networks and industry connections. The primary aim was to collect valuable information on potential stakeholders who could contribute to the project's goals of advancing antibiofilm technologies and fostering academia-industry collaboration.

The questionnaire was designed to assess several key factors, including the technical expertise of industrial actors in fields relevant to *InnovAntiBiofilm*, their market influence, and their capability for commercialisation. It also sought to evaluate stakeholders' prior engagement with biofilm-related research and innovation, their interest in collaborative projects, and their ability to support the scaling-up of project outcomes. As a result of this process, consortium partners identified an initial list of twelve organisations they considered particularly important due to their relevance, expertise, or strategic positioning in the field. By gathering input from consortium members with direct industry experience, this step helped establish a well-rounded preliminary database of potential partners, ensuring that only the most relevant and impactful organisations were considered for inclusion in the stakeholder catalogue.

The full survey template used for collecting this information is provided in **Annex 1**.

b) Online Research and Database Screening

Beyond leveraging consortium networks, KPMG conducted systematic online research and database screening to expand the pool of identified industrial stakeholders. This research focused on identifying

companies, research institutes, and industrial partners actively biotechnology, pharmaceuticals, agriculture and food and feed, healthcare, materials science, and regulatory affairs. These sectors were prioritised as they represent domains where biofilm challenges are particularly relevant and where project outcomes have significant potential for impact.

To ensure a data-driven and objective approach, the team utilised multiple complementary sources to identify and assess relevant stakeholders. The Enterprise Europe Network (EEN)³, a well-established European platform that connects businesses and research institutions looking for collaboration opportunities, was consulted to identify organisations with active interests in relevant fields. The CORDIS⁴ database, which provides detailed information on organisations participating in EU-funded projects, was consulted to identify companies that have previously engaged in biofilm-related research or antimicrobial resistance initiatives.

In parallel, KPMG used an intelligence tool aggregating comprehensive data on innovation funding, research projects, and R&D actors across Europe. Through this tool, the team identified the Top 50 EU Funding Innovators, ranked by the largest grant amounts secured, based in Portugal, France, and Germany, and operating within the Agriculture & Food and Feed, Biotechnology, and Pharmaceutical & Healthcare sectors. This selection was refined to include only private companies, SMEs, and research organisations. These criteria were applied to ensure that the organisations considered for inclusion demonstrated both thematic relevance to *InnovAntiBiofilm* and a proven capacity to attract funding and engage in collaborative innovation. The resulting list was carefully reviewed and analysed to prioritise those stakeholders most strategically aligned with the project's objectives and most likely to contribute meaningfully to its success.

This enabled the project to map influential, high-performing entities that align with *InnovAntiBiofilm*'s goals and prioritise them for stakeholder engagement and outreach.

Contact Information and Engagement Readiness: As part of this process, the project team gathered publicly available contact information for nearly all identified stakeholders. Contact details such as email addresses and websites were obtained from open-access sources, including company websites and public directories. However, for 67 entities, it was not possible to retrieve direct contact information due to restricted access (*e.g.*, blocked websites, absence of public emails, or the requirement to fill out web forms to be contacted). Although we did not include manually gathered contact details in the public version of the catalogue to preserve clarity and consistency, this information is stored securely in the project's internal stakeholder database. These contacts will be used for targeted engagement activities as outlined in Section 6.1 – *Mechanisms for engaging stakeholders in project activities*. For the entities for which contact details could not be retrieved at this stage, the team will continue to investigate alternative channels to enable their future involvement.

4.2. Criteria for selection

The selection of industrial stakeholders for the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project follows a structured and systematic approach to ensure alignment with the project's objectives. The criteria focus on identifying companies and organisations that can contribute to research, development, validation, and commercialisation of antibiofilm technologies. The following criteria were used for selection:

- a) **Relevance to Biofilm-Related Challenges** - Selected stakeholders must demonstrate a direct or indirect involvement in addressing biofilm-related challenges, as detailed in 3.1 Key Industrial Sectors.
- b) **Market Influence and Industrial Impact** - To ensure the scalability and applicability of *InnovAntiBiofilm* solutions, stakeholders must ideally have:
 - A strong presence in relevant industry sectors.
 - Market influence that can facilitate the adoption of new technologies.
 - A distribution network that can accelerate commercialisation.
- c) **Capacity for Research Collaboration** - The ability and willingness of stakeholders to engage in

³ <https://een.ec.europa.eu/>

⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/>

collaborative research and development are critical for effective knowledge transfer. Selected organisations must ideally:

- Have R&D departments or innovation units engaged in related technological developments.
 - Show interest in co-developing new solutions, testing, and validating research outputs.
 - Demonstrate previous participation in research collaborations, particularly within EU-funded programmes.
- d) Regulatory and Compliance Expertise** - Given the importance of regulatory approvals for new antimicrobial solutions, stakeholders must ideally:
- Have knowledge of relevant regulatory frameworks (*e.g.*, EMA, FDA, REACH).
 - Be able to guide compliance processes for new products entering the market.
 - Support the development of industry standards for antibiofilm technologies.
- e) Commitment to Sustainability and Innovation** - Selected industrial partners should ideally align with the European Union's sustainability goals and demonstrate:
- A commitment to reducing environmental impact in their operations.
 - Interest in sustainable alternatives for antimicrobial solutions.
 - Compliance with circular economy principles and green innovation.
- f) Geographic and Sectoral Representation** - To ensure a broad impact and effective collaboration, stakeholders were selected to reflect:
- **A diverse range of industrial sectors**, including biotechnology, pharmaceuticals, agriculture and food and feed, healthcare, materials science, and regulatory affairs. This diversity ensures that the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project addresses biofilm-related challenges across multiple industries, maximising the potential for innovation and commercialisation.
 - **Geographical distribution across different EU countries**, with a particular focus on engaging stakeholders from the countries involved in the project consortium (*Portugal, France, Germany*) Involving industrial partners from these countries is crucial for:
 - Strengthening local and regional synergies between academia and industry within the countries represented in the consortium.
 - Facilitating knowledge transfer and leveraging existing national and European funding mechanisms.
 - Enhancing the local and regional impact of the project by ensuring that results are tested and validated in real-world industrial environments within the participating countries.
 - Supporting long-term sustainability by fostering partnerships that can continue beyond the project's duration.

By prioritising industrial stakeholders from *Portugal, France, and Germany*, *InnovAntiBiofilm* ensures that project outputs remain aligned with national and EU research and innovation priorities while promoting a collaborative European approach to tackling biofilm resistance.

By applying these selection criteria, *InnovAntiBiofilm* ensures that the most relevant stakeholders are engaged in the project, promoting successful collaboration between academia and industry.

4.3. Stakeholder classification system

InnovAntiBiofilm adopts a stakeholder classification system that categorises stakeholders based on their sector, geographical presence, expertise, and potential role in the project. This classification ensures that interactions with stakeholders are targeted and aligned with project objectives.

1. Sector-Based Classification

Industrial stakeholders are grouped based on their primary sector of operation, ensuring that the project addresses biofilm-related challenges across multiple industries:

- **Biotechnology** – Companies specialising in bio-based technologies, bioengineering, and applied

microbiology research that contribute to the development of novel antibiofilm solutions.

- **Pharmaceuticals & Healthcare** – Industry players involved in the development of antibiotic adjuvants, antimicrobial coatings, and infection prevention solutions.
- **Agriculture & Food and Feed Industry** – Stakeholders focused on mitigating biofilm formation in food and feed production, packaging, and water management systems.

2. Geographical Distribution

Stakeholders are also classified based on their country of operation, with a priority on companies from the consortium countries (*Portugal, France, Germany*), ensuring strong regional engagement and alignment with national research and innovation priorities. This classification helps:

- Strengthen collaboration within the consortium and maximise the impact of research outcomes in the participating countries.
- Foster partnerships that contribute to the European Research and Innovation Agenda.
- Facilitate industry-driven validation of research findings in real-world settings within the project's key geographical areas.

3. Function-Based Classification

- **Research & Development Partners:** Companies and institutions actively investing in novel antibiofilm technologies, including biotech firms, pharmaceutical companies, and research institutions. Responsible for developing innovative compounds, formulations, and biofilm prevention strategies.
- **Solution Validators & Testing Partners:** Industrial partners with testing facilities capable of evaluating the effectiveness, safety, and scalability of antibiofilm technologies. Includes clinical research organisations, pharmaceutical validation labs, and industrial testing facilities.
- **Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners:** Organisations involved in scaling up production and bringing antibiofilm technologies to the market. Includes manufacturers of biomaterials, coatings, medical devices, and industrial biocides.
- **Regulatory & Policy Advisors:** Stakeholders specialising in navigating regulatory pathways and ensuring compliance with EU and international standards for new antimicrobial solutions. Includes government agencies, industry regulatory bodies, and legal consultants.
- **Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts:** Companies and entities experienced in bridging the gap between research and commercialisation, including IP management, licensing, and industry partnerships.

By employing this multi-dimensional classification system, *InnovAntiBiofilm* ensures that industrial engagement is well-structured, targeted, and aligned with the project's strategic goals. This approach facilitates efficient knowledge transfer, enhances commercialisation potential, and fosters sustainable academia-industry collaboration.

5. Catalogue of Stakeholders – Summary

A complete list of all stakeholders identified, including detailed profiles, is provided in Annex 2.

5.1. Sector-based Categories

Figure 1 provides a visual representation of the distribution of stakeholders according to their main sector of activity. As illustrated, the majority of stakeholders identified are active in the biotechnology and pharmaceutical sectors, with substantial representation also observed among organisations working across multiple domains such as agriculture and food and feed. This distribution highlights the project's focus on engaging stakeholders whose expertise spans key areas where biofilm-related challenges are most critical and where *InnovAntiBiofilm's* solutions are likely to have the highest impact.

Figure 1 – Number of stakeholders identified per sector

5.2. Geographical Distribution

Figure 2 shows a representation of the geographical distribution of stakeholders across the countries prioritised by the project. Stakeholders are predominantly based in France, Germany, and Portugal, reflecting the strategic focus on countries represented within the consortium. This geographic coverage ensures strong regional engagement and facilitates collaboration within established innovation ecosystems in each country.

Figure 2 - Distribution of stakeholders identified per country

5.3. Function-Based Classification

Figure 3 presents a classification of stakeholders based on their primary function within the innovation and commercialisation value chain. According to this analysis, most stakeholders were classified as research and development partners or solution validators and testing partners, demonstrating a clear emphasis on organisations capable of supporting the validation and further development of antibiofilm technologies. The presence of manufacturing, commercialisation, regulatory, and technology transfer stakeholders further underscores the project’s comprehensive approach to enabling exploitation and adoption of its outcomes.

Figure 3 - Number of stakeholders identified per function

6. Engagement Strategies

This section describes how *InnovAntiBiofilm* will operationalise the engagement of industrial stakeholders identified in this catalogue, ensuring their active participation in project activities and laying the foundation for long-term collaboration beyond the project's duration.

6.1. Mechanisms for engaging stakeholders in project activities

Engagement will be based on clear, accessible activities and communication tools. Stakeholders identified in this catalogue will be invited to participate in one or more of the following actions:

- **Subscription to the Project Newsletter:** UPORTO will contact the stakeholders identified and invite them to subscribe to the *InnovAntiBiofilm* newsletter, which will provide updates on project progress, funding opportunities, training events, and relevant publications.
- **Participation in Thematic Workshops:** Over the course of the project, a series of thematic workshops will be organised (online and/or in-person), covering topics such as:
 - Plant-based antibiofilm strategies,
 - Regulatory considerations in antimicrobial innovation,
 - Technology transfer and commercialisation opportunities.

Stakeholders will be invited to attend, contribute their perspectives, and explore potential synergies.

- **Expert Visits and Demonstration Activities:** Selected stakeholders expressing particular interest will be invited to participate in demonstration sessions or expert visits, offering insights into the research activities and emerging results.
- **Consultations and Surveys:** Surveys and consultations may be carried out periodically in connection with stakeholder interactions to gather input on industrial challenges, needs, and priorities related to antibiofilm technologies. The insights collected will help inform and refine the project's exploitation and sustainability plans.
- **Training Events and Capacity Building:** Stakeholders will be informed about training opportunities organised within the project, including:
 - The Winter School on antibiotic boosters and biofilm resistance (planned for Month 18), and
 - The Summer School on high-throughput screening and development of antibiofilm solutions (planned for Month 32).

Participation will be voluntary and open to all interested organisations.

- **Dissemination and Communication Materials:** Stakeholders will be encouraged to share project materials, such as infographics, leaflets, and publications, within their professional networks to enhance outreach and awareness.
- **Direct Outreach to High-Potential Companies:** While structured research and database screening provide a strong foundation for identifying relevant stakeholders, direct outreach plays a critical role in engaging companies with the highest potential to contribute to *InnovAntiBiofilm*. The project team will seek to proactively reach out to companies with a strong track record in antimicrobial and biofilm research, particularly those with experience in EU-funded projects under Horizon Europe. These efforts will target companies capable of co-developing, validating, or commercialising antibiofilm technologies, and aim to establish early-stage bilateral conversations with industrial actors who are strategically aligned with the project's scientific and exploitation objectives.
- **Snowball Sampling and Peer Recommendations:** To further diversify and strengthen the stakeholder network, *InnovAntiBiofilm* also employs snowball sampling. Through this approach, already identified stakeholders and consortium partners are encouraged to suggest additional organisations that may not have been captured through initial research. This helps uncover high-potential SMEs, start-ups, and niche actors with specialised expertise in antimicrobial innovation and biofilm control. The iterative nature of this method ensures continuous enrichment of the stakeholder pool and supports the project's broader goals of industrial engagement and long-term sustainability.

Engagement will remain flexible, recognising that stakeholders differ in their levels of interest, resources, and capacity to participate. Participation in activities will be voluntary, and the consortium will ensure clear, regular communication to facilitate involvement.

6.2. Long-term collaboration plans

To promote sustainability and extend the impact of *InnovAntiBiofilm* beyond the project's lifetime, the following practical actions are planned:

- **Stakeholder Mailing List and Continued Communication:** A mailing list will be maintained beyond the project end to provide stakeholders with access to public deliverables, project outcomes, and relevant follow-up opportunities.
- **Consultation on Future Funding and Collaboration:** During the final year, stakeholders will be consulted regarding interest in participating in future project proposals, demonstration activities, or joint funding applications under relevant EU programmes (e.g., Horizon Europe, EIC Pathfinder, CBE JU).
- **Promotion of Bilateral and Multilateral Cooperation:** Organisations expressing strong interest will be encouraged to explore Memoranda of Understanding or cooperation agreements with consortium partners to advance shared objectives.
- **Continued Access to Knowledge Resources:** The project website and selected communication channels will remain online for a defined period after project completion, to ensure easy access to training materials, publications, and exploitation guidance.

These actions are designed to maintain momentum, encourage the uptake of results, and build a community of practice focused on antibiofilm innovation.

7. Outcomes and Insights

The preparation of this Catalogue has produced several outcomes that will support the effective implementation of *InnovAntiBiofilm*'s engagement and exploitation activities:

- **Comprehensive Mapping of Relevant Stakeholders:** A total of 306 industrial stakeholders were identified and profiled, spanning domains such as bioprocess engineering, phytochemical production, antimicrobial R&D, and regulatory consultancy. This mapping provides a solid foundation for targeted communication and future collaboration.
- **Identification of Priority Areas for Engagement:** Early feedback and desk research indicate strong interest in:

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- Sustainable biosynthesis of antimicrobial agents,
- Scalable production processes,
- Validation strategies for plant-derived antibiofilm compounds.

These areas will be prioritised in thematic workshops and training sessions.

- **Enhanced Understanding of Potential Adoption Barriers:** Insights gathered during this exercise highlight potential challenges, including:
 - Regulatory uncertainty around novel antimicrobial adjuvants,
 - Scale-up and cost-effectiveness considerations,
 - Need for robust evidence of efficacy and safety.

These factors will be considered in the design of engagement activities and in the exploitation roadmap.

- **Establishment of Initial Contact Channels:** Contact details were collected (where available), and initial invitations to subscribe to the project newsletter have been prepared. This early communication will help build awareness and trust from the outset.

Next Steps: The consortium will build on these outcomes by:

- Inviting stakeholders to participate in consultations and upcoming training events,
- Providing periodic updates on project progress,
- Collecting additional input to refine the exploitation and sustainability strategy,
- Facilitating targeted matchmaking between stakeholders and project partners as specific results mature.

These efforts will contribute to the overall goal of fostering uptake and impact of *InnovAntiBiofilm's* innovations within the European industrial landscape.

8. Conclusion

This deliverable has provided a structured and comprehensive overview of stakeholders relevant to the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project, focusing on organisations active in biotechnology, pharmaceuticals, agriculture and food and feed, healthcare, materials science, and regulatory affairs. Through a combination of partner consultation, database screening, direct outreach, and peer recommendations, a diverse catalogue of 306 stakeholders was compiled.

The results presented here serve as a foundation for targeted engagement activities and strategic collaboration throughout the project. By aligning identified stakeholders with *InnovAntiBiofilm's* scientific focus and exploitation ambitions, this catalogue supports the consortium's broader objectives related to technology validation, transfer, and sustainable impact.

The catalogue will remain a living resource, updated as needed to reflect new contacts and evolving partnership opportunities. The engagement mechanisms outlined, such as thematic workshops, training events, and ongoing communication, will help ensure meaningful stakeholder participation and contribute to the long-term adoption of project outcomes.

9. Annexes

Annex 1: Survey Template for Stakeholder Identification

Link: [InnovAntiBiofilm - Identification on stakeholders](#)

The purpose of this questionnaire is to identify key industrial stakeholders within the countries represented in InnovAntiBiofilm, prioritising those who can contribute meaningfully to the project and participate in consortium events. Please focus on organisations or companies within Portugal, France or Germany that align with the project's objectives.

When you submit this form, it will not automatically collect your details such as name and email address unless you provide it yourself.

Identifying Key Stakeholders

Please list industrial stakeholders who could significantly contribute to InnovAntiBiofilm's objectives.

We recommend identifying at least three stakeholders to ensure a diverse and impactful network.

(Dependency: Three sets of stakeholder fields will appear by default. Additional fields can be added with a button "Add another stakeholder")

[Repeat the following set of questions for each stakeholder identified.]

1. **Who is the Stakeholder?** _____
2. **What is the stakeholder's expertise/focus that makes their work particularly relevant to InnovAntiBiofilm?**

3. **What are the stakeholder's achievements and/or impacts that makes their work particularly relevant to InnovAntiBiofilm?** _____
4. **In which country are they located?**
 Portugal France Germany
5. **In which city/region are they located?** _____
6. **How broad is their influence?**
 Regional National Global
7. **Are there any existing relationships between this stakeholder and InnovAntiBiofilm partners?**
 Yes (Please describe): _____
 No
 Unsure
8. **How could this stakeholder actively contribute to InnovAntiBiofilm's objectives?**
 Research validation in industrial settings
 Co-development of innovative technologies
 Commercialisation and scaling of solutions
 Providing market insights and strategic alignment
 Offering regulatory guidance and compliance support
 Participating in consortium events (e.g., workshops, knowledge exchange sessions)
 Other (please specify): _____
9. **What specific biofilm-related challenges could this stakeholder help address?**

10. **Why do you think they would be interested in collaborating with InnovAntiBiofilm? Motivation or alignment with project goals:** _____
11. **Add another stakeholder:**
 No

Yes [Repeat the previous set of questions for each stakeholder identified.]

Broadening the National Network

12. Beyond the stakeholders listed previously, are there additional entities you believe should be engaged? These could include emerging organisations or key players in relevant fields.

- Yes [If selected **]
- No

**Cycle:

- a. Name: _____
- b. Location: _____
- c. Expertise: _____
- d. Are there another additional entities you believe should be engaged?:
 - Yes [If selected **]
 - No

13. If you were to prioritize three stakeholders from your country for immediate engagement, who would they be and why? _____

14. Are there any sectors, regions, or specific expertise areas within your country that you feel are underrepresented in InnovAntiBiofilm's stakeholder network? _____

Engaging Stakeholders for Consortium Events

15. From the stakeholders you've identified, which do you think would benefit most from participating in consortium events such as the following?

- **Summer School:** Hands-on laboratory course on "Antibiotherapy and boosters testing to control biofilm resistance mechanisms" (Month 18, UPORTO).
- **Winter School:** High throughput experimentation in the development of antibiotic boosters (Month 32, UPORTO).
- **International Symposium:** Technological Innovations for Sustainable Development of Antimicrobial Therapeutics (Month 36, UPORTO).
- **Thematic Workshops:** Addressing specific biofilm challenges and solutions (organized throughout the project duration).
- **Expert Visits:** Focused sessions with leading scientists and entrepreneurs from relevant industries.

Please consider the stakeholders identified in this questionnaire: _____

16. What strategies would you recommend ensuring their active participation in these events?

17. Do you foresee any challenges in engaging these stakeholders?

- Yes [If yes, please describe the challenges and suggest solutions: _____]
- No

Annex 2: List of Stakeholders

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This annex presents the catalogue of stakeholders identified as relevant to the *InnovAntiBiofilm* project. The table is organized alphabetically by stakeholder name and by country, and includes key details such as website, contact information, region, sector of activity, type of organization (e.g., company, research center, association), and their potential role within the project. This structure facilitates targeted outreach and strategic engagement, supporting the project’s exploitation, validation, and sustainability efforts.

Name	Country	City/Region	Sector	Type of entity	Main Function
4DCELL	France	Montreuil	Biotechnology	SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
ACTA ASSOCIATION DE COORDINATION TECHNIQUE AGRICOLE - LES INSTITUTS TECHNIQUES AGRICOLES	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	National Applied Research Network	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
ADVANCED ACCELERATOR APPLICATIONS	France	Saint Genis Pouilly	Biotechnology	SME (Novartis subsidiary)	Research & Development Partners
ADVICENNE SA	France	Nimes	Pharmaceutical	Biopharma SME	Research & Development Partners
AFFILOGIC	France	Nantes	Biotechnology	SME	Research & Development Partners
AGDATAHUB	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Agri Tech SME	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
AGENCE NATIONALE DE LA SECURITE SANITAIRE DE L ALIMENTATION DE L ENVIRONNEMENT ET DU TRAVAIL	France	Maisons Alfort	Agriculture & Food and Feed	National Public Agency	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
ALGAIA	France	Lannilis	Agriculture & Food and Feed, Biotechnology, Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
ALIRI FRANCE SAS	France	Loos	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
ALKION BIOINNOVATIONS	France	Boulogne Billancourt	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
ANTABIO	France	Labège	Pharmaceutical	Biopharma SME	Research & Development Partners
ANTOFENOL	France	Plestan	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
API AGRO	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Digital Platform / SME	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
APMONIA THERAPEUTICS	France	Reims	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
ARKEMA FRANCE SA	France	Puteaux, La Defense	Biotechnology, Pharmaceutical	Industrial Group	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
ARTTIC	France	Paris	Biotechnology	Consultancy	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
ARVALIS INSTITUT DU VEGETAL	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Agricultural Technical Institute	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
ASSISTANCE PUBLIQUE HOPITAUX DE PARIS	France	Paris	Pharmaceutical	University Hospital Network	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
ASSOCIATION GENETHON	France	Evry	Pharmaceutical	Nonprofit Biotech	Research & Development Partners
AYMING	France	Levallois-Perret	Biotechnology	Consultancy	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
BIOECONOMY FOR CHANGE	France	Barenton Bugny	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Innovation Cluster	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
BIOMATLANTE	France	Vigneux De Bretagne	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners

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BIOMERIEUX SA	France	Marcy L'etoile	Biotechnology	Industrial Company	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
CENTRE DE COOPERATION INTERNATIONALE EN RECHERCHE AGRONOMIQUE POUR LEDEVELOPPEMENT - C.I.R.A.D. EPIC	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Public Research Institution	Research & Development Partners
CENTRE DE RECHERCHE DE L'INSTITUT LYFE	France	Ecully	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Higher Education Institution	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
CENTRE DE RECHERCHE ET DE DEVELOPPEMENT DES ANATIDES DU COURTALET	France	Toulouse	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
CENTRE EUROPEEN DE RECHERCHE EN BIOLOGIE ET MEDECINE	France	Illkirch Graffenstaden	Pharmaceutical	Biomedical Research Infrastructure	Research & Development Partners
CENTRE HOSPITALIER UNIVERSITAIRE DE LIMOGES	France	Limoges	Pharmaceutical	University Hospital	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
CENTRE HOSPITALIER UNIVERSITAIRE DE NICE	France	Nice	Pharmaceutical	University Hospital	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
CENTRE HOSPITALIER UNIVERSITAIRE MONTPELLIER	France	Montpellier	Pharmaceutical	University Hospital	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
CENTRE INTERNATIONAL DE HAUTES ETUDES AGRONOMIQUES MEDITERRANEENNES	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Intergovernmental Organisation	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed, Pharmaceutical	National Research Organization	Research & Development Partners
CENTRE NATIONAL INTERPROFESSIONNELDE L'ECONOMIE LAITIERE	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Interprofessional Organisation	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
CENTRE TECHNIQUE DE L INDUSTRIE DESPAPIERS CARTONS ET CELLULOSES	France	Gieres	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Technical Centre	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
CENTRE TECHNIQUE DE LA CONSERVATION DES PRODUITS AGRICOLES	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Technical Centre	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
CENTRE TECHNIQUE INDUSTRIEL DE LA PLASTURGIE ET DES COMPOSITES	France	Bellignat	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Technical Centre	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
CENTRE TECHNIQUE INTERPROFESSIONNEL DES FRUITS ET LEGUMES	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Technical Centre	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
CHERRY BIOTECH	France	Montreuil	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
CIRCA SUSTAINABLE CHEMICALS FRANCE SAS	France	Nancy	Pharmaceutical	Green Chemistry Company	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
CIS BIO INTERNATIONAL SAS	France	Gif Sur Yvette Cedex	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
COMPAGNIE INDUSTRIELLE DE LA MATIERE VEGETAL CIM V	France	Neuilly Sur Seine	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
CORE BIOGENESIS	France	Illkirch Graffenstaden	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
DEFYMED	France	Strasbourg	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
DEPIXUS	France	Paris	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
ECOLE SUPERIEURE DES TECHNOLOGIES INDUSTRIELLES AVANCEES	France	Bidart	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Engineering School & Research Centre	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
ENGIE	France	Courbevoie	Biotechnology	Industrial Group	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners

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ENOBRAQ	France	Ramonville Sainte Agne	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
ENYO PHARMA	France	Lyon	Pharmaceutical	Biopharma SME	Research & Development Partners
EUROPEAN MARINE BIOLOGICAL RESOURCE CENTRE EUROPEAN RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE CONSORTIUM	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	European Research Infrastructure	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
EVONIK ADVANCED BOTANICALS	France	Evry	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
EXTRASYNTHÈSE SAS	France	Genay	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
FABENTECH	France	Lyon	Pharmaceutical	Biopharma SME	Research & Development Partners
FERMENTALG SA	France	Libourne	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
FIBRES RECHERCHE DEVELOPPEMENT-CONSTRUCTION DURABLE ET ECOMATERIAUX	France	Rosieres Pres Troyes	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
FIRALIS MOLECULAR PRECISION SA	France	Huningue	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
FLUIGENT SA	France	Le Kremlin-Bicetre	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
FONDATION CARDIOMETABOLISME NUTRITION	France	Paris	Pharmaceutical	Research Foundation	Research & Development Partners
FONDATION INSTITUT DE RECHERCHE POUR LE DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE ET LES RELATIONS INTERNATIONALES	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Think Tank / Policy Research	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
FONDATION JEAN JACQUES LAFFONT, TOULOUSE SCIENCES ECONOMIQUES	France	Toulouse	Pharmaceutical	Academic Research Institute	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
FOVEA PHARMACEUTICALS	France	France	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
GAC	France	Issy Les Moulineaux	Biotechnology	Consultancy	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
GENOPTICS SA	France	Orsay	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
GEOSYS	France	Balma	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Agri Tech SME	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
GROUPE D'ETUDE ET DE CONTROLE DES VARIETES ET DES SEMENCES	France	Beaucouze	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Public Research Group	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
IFIP-INSTITUT DU PORC ASSOCIATION	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Technical Institute	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
INOREVIA	France	Paris	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
INSTITUT DE L'ELEVAGE	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Livestock R&D Institute	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
INSTITUT DES CORPS GRAS	France	Canejan	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Technical Institute	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
INSTITUT FRANCAIS DE LA VIGNE ET DU VIN	France	Le Grau Du Roi	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Technical Institute	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
INSTITUT FRANCAIS DE RECHERCHE POUR L'EXPLOITATION DE LA MER	France	Plouzane	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE L ENVIRONNEMENT INDUSTRIEL ET DES RISQUES - INERIS	France	Verneuil En Halatte	Pharmaceutical	Public Research Institute	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE LA SANTE ET DE LA RECHERCHE MEDICALE	France	Paris	Pharmaceutical	National Health Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE EN INFORMATIQUE ET AUTOMATIQUE	France	Le Chesnay Cedex	Pharmaceutical	National Research Institute	Research & Development Partners

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INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT	France	Paris Cedex 07	Agriculture & Food and Feed, Pharmaceutical	Public Research Institution	Research & Development Partners
INSTITUT PASTEUR	France	Paris Cedex 15	Pharmaceutical	Public Biomedical Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
INSTITUT TECHNIQUE DE L AGRICULTURE BIOLOGIQUE	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Technical Institute	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
IPSIRIUS	France	Paris	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
KALY-CELL	France	Illkirch Graffenstaden	Biotechnology, Pharmaceutical	SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
L'ORÉAL	France	-	Biotechnology, Pharmaceutical	Industrial Group / Corporation	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
LABORATOIRE NATIONAL DE METROLOGIE ET D'ESSAIS	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	National Metrology & Testing Lab	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
LIPOFABRIK	France	Villeneuve D'ascq	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
LYSOGENE	France	Neuilly Sur Seine	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
MANROS THERAPEUTICS	France	Roscoff	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
MENSIA TECHNOLOGIES	France	Chantepie	Pharmaceutical	MedTech SME	Research & Development Partners
METABOLIC EXPLORER SA	France	Saint Beazire	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
MUTABILIS	France	Romainville	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
NATUREPLAST	France	Mondeville	Agriculture & Food and Feed	SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
NAVAL GROUP	France	Paris	Biotechnology	Industrial Group	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
NOSOPHARM	France	Lyon Cedex 03	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
OLMIX	France	Brehan	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
OWKIN FRANCE	France	Paris	Pharmaceutical	AI / Biotech Company	Research & Development Partners
PELLENC SELECTIVE TECHNOLOGIES	France	Pertuis	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Industrial SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
PHERECYDES PHARMA SA	France	Roscoff	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
QFLUIDICS	France	Strasbourg	Pharmaceutical	MedTech / Imaging	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
RAIDIUM	France	Aubervilliers	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
REGULAXIS	France	Romainville	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
SAMABRIVA	France	Amiens	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
SEPARATIVE	France	Saint Fons	Pharmaceutical	Analytical Tech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
SOCIETE DES SYSTEMES BIOLOGIQUES SARL	France	Apprieu	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
SOLVIONIC	France	Toulouse	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
SYNCHROTRON SOLEIL SOCIETE CIVILE	France	Saint Aubin	Biotechnology	Research Infrastructure	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
SYNOVANCE	France	Bry-Sur-Marne	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
TAFALGIE THERAPEUTICS	France	Marseille	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
TERRES INOVIA	France	Paris	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Agricultural Technical Institute	Solution Validators & Testing Partners

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TOOPI ORGANICS	France	Loupiac-De-La-Reole	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
TREEFROG THERAPEUTICS	France	Pessac	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
UNICANCER	France	Paris	Pharmaceutical	Clinical Network / Federation	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
VALAGRO CARBONE RENOUVELABLE POITOU-CHARENTES	France	Poitiers	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
VALOREX SAS	France	Combourtille	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Agri-Food SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
VER DE TERRE PRODUCTION	France	Breteil	Agriculture & Food and Feed	NGO / Educational Producer	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
ALACRIS THERANOSTICS GMBH	Germany	Berlin	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
ALFRED-WEGENER-INSTITUT HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FUR POLAR- UND MEERESFORSCHUNG	Germany	Bremerhaven	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Marine Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
AQUA-PROTECT GMBH	Germany	Mannheim	Biotechnology	SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
ASA SPEZIALENZYME GMBH	Germany	Wolfenbittel	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
BASF SE	Germany	Ludwigshafen Am Rhein	Agriculture & Food and Feed, Biotechnology	Chemical Industry Leader	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
BAYER AKTIENGESELLSCHAFT	Germany	Leverkusen	Pharmaceutical	Pharmaceutical / Chemical Corporation	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
BAYER TECHNOLOGY SERVICES GMBH	Germany	Leverkusen	Pharmaceutical	Corporate R&D Division	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
BIOZON GMBH	Germany	Bremerhaven	Agriculture & Food and Feed, Biotechnology	Food and Feed Tech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
BITOP AKTIENGESELLSCHAFT	Germany	Witten	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
BRUKER BIOSPIN GMBH & CO KG	Germany	Ettlingen	Pharmaceutical	Analytical Instrumentation	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
BUNDESAMT FUR VERBRAUCHERSCHUTZ UND LEBENSMITTELSICHERHEIT	Germany	Braunschweig	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Federal Authority	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
BUNDESINSTITUT FUR RISIKOBEWERTUNG	Germany	Berlin	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Federal Risk Assessment Authority	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
BUNDESINSTITUT FUR ARZNEIMITTEL UND MEDIZINPRODUKTE	Germany	Bonn	Pharmaceutical	Federal Health Authority	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
BUNDESVERBAND NATURKOST NATURWAREN EV	Germany	Berlin	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Organic Industry Association	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
CASCAT GMBH	Germany	Straubing	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
CEGAT GMBH	Germany	Tubingen	Biotechnology	Biotech SME / Genomics Service Provider	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
CENIX BIOSCIENCE GMBH	Germany	Dresden	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
C-LECTA GMBH	Germany	Leipzig	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
COLLABORATING CENTRE ON SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION AND PRODUCTION GGMBH	Germany	Wuppertal	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Nonprofit Think Tank	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
COLVISTEC AG	Germany	Berlin	Pharmaceutical	Tech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
COMPUTOMICS GMBH	Germany	Tubingen	Biotechnology	Agri Bioinformatics SME	Research & Development Partners
CORTEC GMBH	Germany	Freiburg Im Breisgau	Pharmaceutical	MedTech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners

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DECHEMA GESELLSCHAFT FUR CHEMISCHE TECHNIK UND BIOTECHNOLOGIE	Germany	Frankfurt	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Scientific Society / R&D Platform	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
DEUTSCHES INSTITUT FUER ERNAHRUNGSFORSCHUNG POTSDAM REHBRUECKE	Germany	Nuthetal	Pharmaceutical	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
DEUTSCHES KREBSFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM HEIDELBERG	Germany	Heidelberg	Pharmaceutical	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
DEUTSCHES PRIMATENZENTRUM GMBH	Germany	Gottingen	Pharmaceutical	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
DEUTSCHES ZENTRUM FUR LUFT - UND RAUMFAHRT EV	Germany	Koln	Agriculture & Food and Feed	National Aerospace Research Center	Research & Development Partners
DEUTSCHES ZENTRUM FUR NEURODEGENERATIVE ERKRANKUNGEN EV	Germany	Bonn	Pharmaceutical	Public Research Centre	Research & Development Partners
DIATOPE GMBH	Germany	Ummendorf	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
DIL DEUTSCHES INSTITUT FUR LEBENSMITTELTECHNIK EV	Germany	Quakenbruck	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Food and Feed Tech Research Institute	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
DMT GMBH & CO. KG	Germany	Essen	Biotechnology	Engineering / Technical Services	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
DR. BRILL + PARTNER GMBH INSTITUT FUER HYGIENE UND MIKROBIOLOGIE	Germany	Hamburg	Biotechnology	Research / Testing Institute	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
DWI LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR INTERAKTIVE MATERIALIEN EV	Germany	Aachen	Pharmaceutical	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
ECOLOGIC INSTITUT GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH	Germany	Berlin	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Environmental Policy Think Tank	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
EEMAGINE MEDICAL IMAGING SOLUTIONSGMBH	Germany	Berlin	Biotechnology	MedTech / Neuroimaging SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
E-NEMA GESELLSCHAFT FUER BIOTECHNOLOGIE UND BIOLOGISCHEN PFLANZENSCHUTZ MBH	Germany	Schwentinental	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
ENZYMICALS AG	Germany	Greifswald	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
EUROPEAN CENTER FOR AGRICULTURAL, REGIONAL AND ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY RESEARCH, EUROCARE	Germany	Bonn	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Academic Policy Institute	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
EUROPEAN MOLECULAR BIOLOGY LABORATORY	Germany	Heidelberg	Agriculture & Food and Feed, Biotechnology, Pharmaceutical	International Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
EUROPEAN VACCINE INITIATIVE E.V	Germany	Heidelberg	Pharmaceutical	Nonprofit / R&D Consortium	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
EVONIK INDUSTRIES AG	Germany	Essen	Pharmaceutical	Industrial Chemistry / Life Sciences Company	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
EVONIK OPERATIONS GMBH	Germany	Essen	Biotechnology	Industrial Chemical & Biotech Company	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
FORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUR BIOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU DEUTSCHLAND EV	Germany	Frankfurt Am Main	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Applied Research Institute	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
FORSCHUNGSVERBUND BERLIN EV	Germany	Berlin	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Research Consortium	Research & Development Partners
G.E.O.S.INGENIEURGESELLSCHAFT MBH	Germany	Halsbrucke	Biotechnology	Environmental Engineering SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
GEA WESTFALIA SEPARATOR GROUP GMBH	Germany	Oelde	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Industrial Engineering Company	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
GENEART AG	Germany	Regensburg	Biotechnology	Biotech Company	Research & Development Partners
GENOME BIOLOGICS UG	Germany	Kronberg Im Taunus	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
GENXPRO GMBH	Germany	Frankfurt	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
GFZ HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FUR GEOFORSCHUNG	Germany	Potsdam	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners

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GREEN CITY SOLUTIONS GMBH	Germany	Bestensee	Biotechnology	Urban Tech / Environmental SME	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
HELMHOLTZ ZENTRUM MUENCHEN DEUTSCHES FORSCHUNGSZENTRUM FUER GESUNDHEIT UND UMWELT GMBH	Germany	Neuherberg	Pharmaceutical	Public Research Centre	Research & Development Partners
HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FUR INFEKTIONSFORSCHUNG GMBH	Germany	Braunschweig	Pharmaceutical	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FUR OZEANFORSCHUNG KIEL (GEOMAR)	Germany	Kiel	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Marine Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM FUR UMWELTFORSCHUNG GMBH - UFZ	Germany	Leipzig	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
HQS QUANTUM SIMULATIONS GMBH	Germany	Karlsruhe	Biotechnology	Deep Tech SME	Research & Development Partners
IMMATICS BIOTECHNOLOGIES GMBH	Germany	Tuebingen	Pharmaceutical	Biopharma SME	Research & Development Partners
INSILICO BIOTECHNOLOGY AG	Germany	Stuttgart	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
INSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE STRUKTURFORSCHUNG EV	Germany	Frankfurt Am Main	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Socio-Economic Research Institute	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
INSTITUT FUER MIKROTECHNIK MAINZ GMBH	Germany	Mainz	Pharmaceutical	Tech R&D SME	Research & Development Partners
INSTITUT FÜR ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMTECHNIK BREMEN GMBH	Germany	Bremen	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Applied Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
INSTITUT FUR LEBENSMITTEL- UND UMWELTFORSCHUNG EV	Germany	Bad Belzig	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Applied Research Institute	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
IO BIOFILMENTFERNER	Germany	Melsungen	Biotechnology	SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
ITHERA MEDICAL GMBH	Germany	Munchen	Biotechnology	MedTech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
JENABIOS GMBH	Germany	Jena	Biotechnology	Bioeconomy / SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
JENLAB GMBH	Germany	Berlin	Pharmaceutical	MedTech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
JOHANN HEINRICH VON THUENEN-INSTITUT, BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUER LAENDLICHE RAEUME, WALD UND FISCHEREI	Germany	Braunschweig	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Federal Research Institute	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
JULIUS KUHN-INSTITUT BUNDESFORSCHUNGSINSTITUT FUR KULTURPFLANZEN	Germany	Quedlinburg	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Federal Research Institute	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
JUNO THERAPEUTICS GMBH	Germany	Gottingen	Pharmaceutical	Biopharma (subsidiary of Bristol Myers Squibb)	Research & Development Partners
KUBERMATIC GMBH	Germany	Hamburg	Pharmaceutical	Software SME	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
KWS SAAT SE & CO KGAA	Germany	Einbeck	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Seed Industry Company	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
LEIBNIZ - INSTITUT FUER PFLANZENGENETIK UND KULTURPFLANZENFORSCHUNG	Germany	Seeland Ot Gatersleben	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
LEIBNIZ INSTITUT FUER KATALYSE EV	Germany	Rostock	Pharmaceutical	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUER AGRARENTWICKLUNG IN TRANSFORMATIONSOEKONOMIEN (IAMO)	Germany	Halle Saale	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Public Research Institute	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR AGRARTECHNIK UND BIOOKONOMIE EV	Germany	Potsdam	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Applied Research Institute	Research & Development Partners

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LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR GEMUSE- UND ZIERPFLANZENBAU GROSSBEEREN/ERFURT EV	Germany	Grossbeeren	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
LEIBNIZ-INSTITUT FUR PFLANZENBIOCHEMIE	Germany	Halle	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
LEIBNIZ-ZENTRUM FUER AGRARLANDSCHAFTSFORSCHUNG (ZALF) E.V.	Germany	Muencheberg	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
LENIOBIO GMBH	Germany	Dusseldorf	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
LIFEGLIMMER GMBH	Germany	Berlin	Biotechnology	Bioinformatics / Systems Biology SME	Research & Development Partners
LIPOTYPE	Germany	Dresden	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
MAX PLANCK INSTITUT FUER KOHLENFORSCHUNG	Germany	Muelheim An Der Ruhr	Pharmaceutical	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
MERCK KOMMANDITGESELLSCHAFT AUF AKTIEN	Germany	Darmstadt	Biotechnology	Life Science & Pharma MNC	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
MICROFLUIDIC CHIPSHOP GMBH	Germany	Jena	Biotechnology	Microfluidics / SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
MILTENYI BIOTEC GMBH	Germany	Bergish Gladbach	Biotechnology	Biotech Company	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
MOLECULAR NETWORKS GMBH COMPUTERCHEMIE	Germany	Nurnberg	Pharmaceutical	Cheminformatics SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
MUKOCELL GMBH	Germany	Dortmund	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
MUSHLABS GMBH	Germany	Hamburg	Biotechnology	Food and Feed Tech / Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
MYBIOTECH GMBH	Germany	Uberherrn	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
NANOSCALE SYSTEMS, NANOSS GMBH	Germany	Darmstadt	Biotechnology	Deep Tech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
NANOTAG BIOTECHNOLOGIES GMBH	Germany	Gottingen	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
NANOTECMARIN GMBH	Germany	Ingelheim Am Rhein	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
NATURLAND - VERBAND FUR OKOLOGISCHEN LANDBAU EV	Germany	Munchen	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Organic Farming Association	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
NATURWISSENSCHAFTLICHES UND MEDIZINISCHES INSTITUT AN DER UNIVERSITAET TUEBINGEN	Germany	Reutlingen	Pharmaceutical	Applied Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
NEC LABORATORIES EUROPE GMBH	Germany	Heidelberg	Biotechnology	Corporate R&D Lab	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
NORDDEUTSCHE PFLANZENZUCHT HANS-GEORG LEMBKE KG	Germany	Holtsee	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Plant Breeding Company	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
NUVISAN ICB GMBH	Germany	Berlin	Pharmaceutical	Contract Research Organisation (CRO)	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
OSYPKA AG	Germany	Rheinfelden Baden	Pharmaceutical	MedTech Company	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
PFEIFER & LANGEN GMBH & CO KG	Germany	Koln	Biotechnology	Industrial Group	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
PHILIPS TECHNOLOGIE GMBH	Germany	Hamburg	Pharmaceutical	HealthTech / Electronics Corporation	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
POTSDAM-INSTITUT FUR KLIMAFOLGENFORSCHUNG EV	Germany	Potsdam	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Climate Research Institute	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
PRESENS PRECISION SENSING GMBH	Germany	Regensburg	Biotechnology	Sensor Technology SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
PROCTER & GAMBLE SERVICES COMPANY GMBH, DEUTSCHLAND	Germany	Schwalbach Am Taunus	Biotechnology, Pharmaceutical	Industrial Group / Corporation	Solution Validators & Testing Partners

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PROSION GMBH	Germany	Koln	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
PROTEOME SCIENCES R&D GMBH & CO. KG	Germany	Frankfurt	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
QIAGEN GMBH	Germany	Hilden	Pharmaceutical	Biotech Multinational	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
RESUSCITEC GMBH	Germany	Freiburg Im Breisgau	Pharmaceutical	MedTech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
ROBERT BOSCH GESELLSCHAFT FUR MEDIZINISCHE FORSCHUNG MBH	Germany	Stuttgart	Pharmaceutical	Research Foundation	Research & Development Partners
SANOFI-AVENTIS DEUTSCHLAND GMBH	Germany	Frankfurt Am Main	Pharmaceutical	Pharmaceutical Company	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
SESAM-BIOTECH GMBH	Germany	Aachen	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
SOEX TEXTIL-VERMARKTUNGSGESELLSCHAFT MBH	Germany	Ahrensburg	Biotechnology	Private company	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
SUDZUCKER AG	Germany	Mannheim	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Food and Feed Industry Company	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
TRIFOLIO-M GMBH	Germany	Lahnau	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
UMWELT- UND INGENIEURTECHNIK GMBH DRESDEN	Germany	Dresden	Biotechnology	IT / Research SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
VDI/VDE INNOVATION + TECHNIK GMBH	Germany	Berlin	Agriculture & Food and Feed, Biotechnology	Innovation Agency	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
VEREIN ZUR FORDERUNG DES TECHNOLOGIETRANSFERS AN DER HOCHSCHULE BREMERHAVEN EV	Germany	Bremerhaven	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Technology Transfer Association	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
VIVASCOPE GMBH	Germany	Munich	Biotechnology	Imaging Tech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
WUPPERTAL INSTITUT FUR KLIMA, UMWELT, ENERGIE GGMBH	Germany	Wuppertal	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Environmental Think Tank	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
A4F ALGA FUEL SA	Portugal	Lisboa	Agriculture & Food and Feed, Biotechnology, Pharmaceutical	Industrial Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
AGRI-CIENCIA CONSULTORES DE ENGENHARIA LDA	Portugal	Évora	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Engineering Consultancy SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
ALFAMA - INVESTIGACAO E DESENVOLVIMENTO DE PRODUTOS FARMACEUTICOS, LDA.	Portugal	Oeiras	Biotechnology	Biopharma SME	Research & Development Partners
ALGAPLUS-PRODUCAO E COMERCIALIZACAODE ALGAS E SEUS DERIVADOS, SA	Portugal	Ílhavo	Agriculture & Food and Feed, Biotechnology, Pharmaceutical	Agri-Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
ALLMICROALGAE NATURAL PRODUCTS SA	Portugal	Pataias	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
APARROZ -AGRUPAMENTO DE PRODUTORESDE ARROZ DO VALE DO SADO LDA	Portugal	Alcácer Do Sal	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Agricultural Cooperative	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
APBIO ASSOCIACAO PORTUGUESA DE BIOINDUSTRIA	Portugal	Cantanhede	Biotechnology	Industry Association	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
ASSOCIACAO BIP4DAB	Portugal	Oeiras	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Patient Advocacy Association	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
ASSOCIACAO FRAUNHOFER PORTUGAL RESEARCH	Portugal	Porto	Pharmaceutical	Applied R&D Institute	Research & Development Partners
BGI SA	Portugal	Lisboa	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Innovation Accelerator	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
BIOALVO S.A	Portugal	Lisboa	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
BIOCANT PARK	Portugal	Cantanhede	Biotechnology	Innovation Cluster / Research Park	Research & Development Partners
BIOFABICS LDA	Portugal	Porto	Biotechnology, Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
BIOTREND-INOVACAO E ENGENHARIA EM BIOTECNOLOGIA SA	Portugal	Cantanhede	Agriculture & Food and Feed, Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners

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BLUEPHARMA	Portugal	Coimbra	Pharmaceutical	Biopharma SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
BNML BEHAVIORAL & MOLECULAR LAB	Portugal	Braga	Pharmaceutical	Academic Lab	Research & Development Partners
CAREDOME PATIENT SUPPORT AND HEALTHCARE SOLUTIONS PORTUGAL LDA	Portugal	Lisboa	Pharmaceutical	Healthcare Service Provider	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
CELL2B ADVANCED THERAPEUTICS SA	Portugal	Cantanhede	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
CENTRO DE CIENCIAS DO MAR DO ALGARVE	Portugal	Faro	Agriculture & Food and Feed, Pharmaceutical	Marine Research Centre	Research & Development Partners
CENTRO DE ESTUDOS SOCIAIS	Portugal	Coimbra	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Social Sciences Research Institute	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
CENTRO DE NEUROCIENCIAS E BIOLOGIACELULAR ASSOCIACAO	Portugal	Coimbra	Pharmaceutical	Academic Research Centre	Research & Development Partners
CENTRO HOSPITALAR DE LISBOA CENTRAL, EPE	Portugal	Lisboa	Pharmaceutical	Public Hospital	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
CENTRO OPERATIVO E DE TECNOLOGIA DE REGADIO ASSOCIACAO	Portugal	Beja	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Agricultural R&D Association	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
CNET CENTRE FOR NEW ENERGY TECHNOLOGIES SA	Portugal	Sacavém E Prior Velho Lisboa	Pharmaceutical	Applied Energy Research Centre	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
CONFAGRI-CONFEDERACAO NACIONAL DAS COOPERATIVAS AGRICOLAS E DO CREDITO AGRICOLA DE PORTUGAL CCRL	Portugal	Lisboa	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Agricultural Confederation	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
COOPERNICO - COOPERATIVA DE DESENVOLVIMENTO SUSTENTAVEL CRL	Portugal	Lisboa	Pharmaceutical	Energy and Sustainability Cooperative	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
DECORGEL PRODUTOS ALIMENTARES SA	Portugal	Maia	Biotechnology	Food and Feed Industry Company	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
DEVAN-MICROPOLIS, SA	Portugal	Maia	Biotechnology	Biotech / Textile Tech Company	Biotech / Textile Tech Company
EXMCEUTICALS PORTUGAL LDA	Portugal	Lisboa	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
EXPERIAN LDA	Portugal	Porto	Biotechnology	ICT / Data Analytics	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
EXTREMOCHEM LDA (HOVIONE)	Portugal	Igrejinha	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
FINAO BIOTECH	Portugal	Alentejo	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
FRUSOAL - FRUTAS SOTAVENTO ALGARVE LDA	Portugal	Algarve	Biotechnology	Agricultural SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
FUNDACAO D. ANNA DE SOMMER CHAMPALIMAUD E DR. CARLOS MONTEZ CHAMPALIMAUD	Portugal	Lisboa	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Biomedical Research Foundation	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
GENE EXPRESS SERVIÇOS GENÓMICOS PARA DIAGNÓSTICO E INVESTIGAÇÃO LDA	Portugal	Alcabideche	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
GENIBET - BIOPHARMACEUTICALS SA	Portugal	Oeiras	Biotechnology	CDMO / Biopharma SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
GROWINGFORMULA LDA	Portugal	Cantanhede	Biotechnology	Agri Tech / Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
HAEDS PORTUGAL LDA	Portugal	Azoia De Cima	Biotechnology	ICT / Engineering SME	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
HOLOSS - HOLISTIC AND ONTOLOGICALSOLUTIONS FOR SUSTAINABILITY, LDA.	Portugal	Monção Viana De Castelo	Pharmaceutical	Sustainability SME	Regulatory & Policy Advisors
HYDRUMEDICAL SA	Portugal	Guimarães	Biotechnology	MedTech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners

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I3S - INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACAO E INOVACAO EM SAUDE DA UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO	Portugal	Porto	Pharmaceutical	Academic Research Centre	Research & Development Partners
IBERAGAR SOCIEDADE LUSO ESPANHOLA DE COLOIDES MARINHOS SA	Portugal	Coina	Biotechnology	Industrial Algae Company	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
ICETA INSTITUTO DE CIENCIAS, TECNOLOGIAS E AGROAMBIENTE DA UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO	Portugal	Porto	Pharmaceutical	Academic Research Unit	Research & Development Partners
INESC ID - INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIA DE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES, INVESTIGACAO E DESENVOLVIMENTO EM LISBOA	Portugal	Lisboa	Pharmaceutical	R&D Institute	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
INGREDIENT ODYSSEY SA	Portugal	Santarém	Biotechnology	Food and Feed Tech SME	Research & Development Partners
INSTITUTO DE BIOLOGIA EXPERIMENTAL E TECNOLOGICA	Portugal	Oeiras	Biotechnology	Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
INSTITUTO DE BIOLOGIA MOLECULAR E CELULAR-IBMC	Portugal	Porto	Pharmaceutical	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
INSTITUTO DE INVESTIGACAO CIENTIFICA TROPICAL	Portugal	Lisboa	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Scientific Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
INSTITUTO DE MEDICINA MOLECULAR JOAO LOBO ANTUNES	Portugal	Lisboa	Pharmaceutical	Academic Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
INSTITUTO DE SAUDE PUBLICA DA UNIVERSIDADE DO PORTO	Portugal	Porto	Biotechnology	Academic Public Health Institute	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
INSTITUTO DE SISTEMAS E ROBOTICA-ASSOCIACAO	Portugal	Coimbra	Pharmaceutical	Academic Research Institute	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE INVESTIGAÇÃO AGRARIA E VETERINARIA	Portugal	Oeiras	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Public Research Institute	Research & Development Partners
INSTITUTO NACIONAL DE RECURSOS BIOLÓGICOS I.P. INRB	Portugal	Lisboa	Pharmaceutical	Innovation & Technology Transfer Institute	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
INSTITUTO PEDRO NUNES ASSOCIACAO PARA A INOVACAO E DESENVOLVIMENTO EM CIENCIA E TECNOLOGIA	Portugal	Coimbra	Pharmaceutical	International Research Centre	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
INTERNATIONAL IBERIAN NANOTECHNOLOGY LABORATORY	Portugal	Braga	Biotechnology	Digital Health SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
IOBUNDLE, LDA	Portugal	Lisboa	Biotechnology	Financial Services / Audit	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
LABORATORIO NACIONAL DE ENERGIA E GEOLOGIA I.P.	Portugal	São Mamede De Infesta	Biotechnology	Industrial Manufacturing Company	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
LANKHORST EURONETE PORTUGAL SA	Portugal	Nogueira - Maia	Biotechnology	Packaging R&D Unit	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
LOGOPLASTE INNOVATION LAB LDA	Portugal	Cascais	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Agro-Food and Feed SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
M. FERREIRA & FILHAS LDA	Portugal	Gimonde Bragança	Biotechnology	MedTech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
MAGNOMICS SA	Portugal	Cantanhede	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
METATISSUE - BIOSOLUTIONS, LDA	Portugal	Ílhavo	Pharmaceutical	Regional R&D Collaborative	Research & Development Partners
MORE - LABORATORIO COLABORATIVO MONTANHAS DE INVESTIGACAO ASSOCIACAO	Portugal	Bragança	Pharmaceutical	Marine Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners

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NATIRIS	Portugal	Lisboa	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
NECTON-COMPANHIA PORTUGUESA DE CULTURAS MARINHAS SA	Portugal	Olhão	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Industrial SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
NGC - NEXT GENERATION CHEMISTRY	Portugal	Porto	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
PATRIMVS INDUSTRIA SA	Portugal	Seia	Biotechnology	Biopharma SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
P-BIO - ASSOCIAÇÃO PORTUGUESA DE BIOINDÚSTRIA	Portugal	Cantanhede	Biotechnology	Industry Association	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
PLUX - WIRELESS BIOSIGNALS S.A.	Portugal	Lisboa	Agriculture & Food and Feed, Pharmaceutical	Chemistry & Technology Research Network	Research & Development Partners
REQUIMTE REDE DE QUIMICA E DE TECNOLOGIA ASSOCIACAO	Portugal	Porto	Agriculture & Food and Feed	CRO / R&D Service SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
RIASEARCH, UNIPESSOAL, LDA	Portugal	Ovar	Biotechnology, Pharmaceutical	Marine Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
SEA4US - BIOTECNOLOGIA E RECURSOS MARINHOS, S.A.	Portugal	Sagres	Pharmaceutical	Tech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
SERENITYCLOUD LDA	Portugal	Carregado	Biotechnology	Unknown / SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
SETENTA E TRES MIL E CEM LDA	Portugal	Igrejinha Évora	Pharmaceutical	Social Innovation SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
SHINE 2EUROPE LDA	Portugal	Coimbra	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
SILICOLIFE LDA	Portugal	Braga	Pharmaceutical	Engineering SME	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
SILICONGATE LDA	Portugal	Porto	Biotechnology	Wine Industry Company	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
SOGRAPE VINHOS SA	Portugal	Avintes	Pharmaceutical	Biotech SME	Research & Development Partners
STAB VIDA INVESTIGACAO E SERVICOS EM CIENCIAS BIOLOGICAS LDA	Portugal	Caparica	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
STEMMATTERS, BIOTECNOLOGIA E MEDICIINA REGENERATIVA SA	Portugal	Barco	Biotechnology	Biotech SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
STEMMATTERS, BIOTECNOLOGIA E MEDICINA REGENERATIVA LDA	Portugal	Porto	Biotechnology	Pulp & Paper Industry	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
TECNIMEDE	Portugal	Lisboa	Pharmaceutical	Biopharma SME	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
THE NAVIGATOR COMPANY SA	Portugal	Setúbal Sado	Biotechnology	Food and Feed Tech SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners
THUNDER FOODS LDA	Portugal	Santarém	Agriculture & Food and Feed	ICT SME	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
UBIWHERE LDA	Portugal	Aveiro	Biotechnology	Analytical Instrumentation Distributor	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
UNICAM SISTEMAS ANALITICOS	Portugal	Algés	Pharmaceutical	Applied Research Institute	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
UNINOVA-INSTITUTO DE DESENVOLVIMENTO DE NOVAS TECNOLOGIAS-ASSOCIACAO	Portugal	Caparica	Agriculture & Food and Feed	Engineering & IoT SME	Technology Transfer & Market Implementation Experts
UNPARALLEL INNOVATION LDA	Portugal	Portimão	Biotechnology	Industrial Manufacturing SME	Manufacturing & Commercialisation Partners
VALBOPAN-FIBRAS DE MADEIRA SA	Portugal	Nazaré	Biotechnology	Agri / Environmental SME	Solution Validators & Testing Partners